

DEVELOPING THE ABILITIES OF GIFTED STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF MODERN BIOLOGICAL EDUCATION DEVELOPMENT OF ABILITIES

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ANNOTATION: This article discusses innovative methods characteristic of modern educators, guidelines for working with gifted students during lessons, and the process of selecting and nurturing talented pupils. In essence, it argues that educational institutions should provide adequate conditions for the development of students' personalities, the realization of their interests and talents, independent learning, and creative work. The article emphasizes the importance of ensuring that students are sufficiently supported with the necessary environment to foster their growth, pursue their interests, showcase their abilities, acquire knowledge independently, and engage in creative endeavors. Talented students in the process of modern biological education to question their abilities.

KEYWORDS: Individual, talent, Genius, Special classifications, Creative endeavors, Natural quality, Data analysis, Scientific-based programs, Creative activities.

Introduction: The National Curriculum emphasizes "improving the methodology for identifying and teaching gifted and talented students, creating psychological, pedagogical, and organizational conditions," which will result in the formation of a national database and monitoring system for gifted youth. It is recommended to involve the best educators and scientists in developing special curricula and progressive pedagogical technologies, ensuring their active participation in the educational process, as well as establishing national (elite) educational institutions such as centers for teaching politics, economics, culture, and art.

The interpretation of talent from a socio-historical and natural perspective indicates that it is an advanced stage in the development of abilities. Talent, derived from the Greek word meaning a valuable, unique thing or hereditary natural quality, is an individual characteristic consisting of a set of abilities and gifts that ensure the successful and creative execution of a particular activity.

Key characteristics of talent:

- a) *ensuring success;*
- b) *independently carry out activities;*
- c) *the presence of an element of originality, consisting of a combination of abilities and talents;*
- d) *Individual psychological qualities;*
- e) *the possibility of creativity, which changes social life.*

Scheme. 1 - bringing talent to the level of talent

The sum of the identified important abilities is brought into being the talent structure of the mind. According to scientific researchers, high talent can consist of stages as follows:

A) the first feature of such a person is elegance, cheapness, readiness to perform serious activities.
 B) the second characteristic of a person is his preparation for Labor (propensity for Labor, aspiration for Labor, transformation of Labor into need).

C) the third feature of a person is the characteristics of thinking in him and the speed of reasoning, the order of reason, the high possibilities of analysis and generalization, the productivity of reason. Data analysis shows that the special talent structure is complemented by a number of abilities that comply with the requirements of specific activities in addition to the above qualities.

The modern world is characterized by the instability and variability of living and working conditions, which puts high demands on its specialists of any profile. In addition to the need to constantly learn and change professionally, a person should also have creative thinking and creative abilities. To solve life tasks and problems, it is necessary not only to have a strong intellect and developed cognitive abilities, but also to be ready for a broad worldview. It is precisely the training of gifted schoolchildren who can perceive, understand these indicators that is becoming our main task, which can get out of an emerging problem situation through highly intelligent and special methods. The Olympic movement of schoolchildren is used not only to search for talented young people, but also to test educational technologies related to the socio-cultural requirements of society.

At this point, "who are talented young people?", the question arises. "Talent" in Arabic is characterized by such qualities as "be able", "Be Able", a concept that means the creative nature and mental activity of a person, as well as the strength of talented young people's desire to pursue a goal, perseverance and hard work, as well as the desire to engage in creative activities. The main purpose of the search,

identification and education of gifted students is to train, help young people with intellectual potential, developing the scientific and creative potential of the Republic, to show and develop their abilities in the relevant areas of knowledge and specific areas of Science for talented people, and to create opportunities for the realization of unique talent in them. That is why the state provides special support for talented young people.

It is assumed that the ideal program for teaching gifted children should meet these requirements. That is, these requirements are perceived as a universal basis in the education of gifted children of preschool age or older school age. These foundations will be the direction that provides an effective result in the education and development of gifted children. The list of requirements for the formation of educational programs created for gifted children should be replenished on the basis of changes in society and the development of educational policy. In ensuring the development of the talent of students with high opportunities, the creation of special educational programs that can meet their requirements and capabilities is considered significant in solving many problems. The emergence of the opportunity to open classes, schools for children with high abilities in our country, the practice of teaching, which ensures the development of the talent of such students, has led to the development of schools, classes, scientific-based programs and educational content. The resulting scientific and practical discontinuity led to negative results, in particular, an imbalance of form and content. There are many special schools, but they have a minority of specially trained teachers and programs approved by the scientific community.

Many psychologist-scientists of our time, especially Americans, believe that within the new diagnostic techniques, biographical questionnaires come to the first plan, since they can be applied to both children and adolescents. They believe that it is more reliable than traditional tests in demonstrating talent opportunities and predicting its achievements. Recognizing the advantage of such a method is that we can quickly understand what is an indicator that makes it possible to show the shortcomings in traditional intelligence and creativity tests and that we should abandon them as soon as possible, as well as introduce it into practice. But it should be remembered that an integrated approach to the manifestation of talent is not completely free from mistakes. As a result, a gifted child may go unnoticed or, on the contrary, gradually lose his will by adding a child to the talented children who cannot justify such an assessment even in his further activities when all the necessary conditions are created for him. Although the non-standard test is spent more time than the ordinary Test, in fact, it contributes to the conscious logical thinking of the student. The large number of correct answers, the need to correctly define them, prompts the reader to take self-control for a while. In a word, it is necessary to create conditions for the development of the personality of students in educational institutions, the realization of their interests, talents, independent knowledge and creative work.

K.Xeller on the results of experimental and test work conducted by **Heller**, the following personal significant aspects from highly gifted middle-level gifted students are distinguished by prognostic indicators - they can be cited as an example of high-level intellectual abilities, abilities of creative content faster than other students, and unique memory, intellectual curiosity and thirst for knowledge, feeling control with, achieving individual effectiveness and independence of thought is the maintenance of a positive academic "I" concept related to self-adequate assessment. Another "five-factor model" specific to determining the nature of giftedness is A.Developed by **Tannenbaum**, he believes that the intellectual, creative qualities that arise do not in themselves guarantee the realization of an individual in creative activity. To do this, the joint action of external and internal factors, which is carried out in five conditional conditions, is assumed. They are counted as: general ability, Ability in specific activities, special classifications of nonintellectual content, stimulating environment, random factors.

Within the framework of the above studies, a wide range of reforms is also being implemented in the educational system of our country. In particular, it is possible to highlight the muane work on the search for talented pupils-young people, the cultivation of their abilities and talent. Talent is a set of processes that consist in demonstrating and developing its unique abilities in the corresponding branches of knowledge and specific areas of educational science, as well as creating opportunities for the emergence of unique talent in them. In short, in general educational schools, it is necessary to create sufficient conditions for the development of the personality of students, their interests in science, realization of their talents, independent knowledge and implementation of creative activities.

It is impossible to create programs that provide creative development of gifted students, scientifically based, on the one hand, without taking into account the general psychological characteristics of creative development and growing up as individuals, on the other hand, without taking into account the specific requirements and capabilities of gifted children. Only when scientific assumptions about the

potential, interest, purpose and requirements that such children can achieve in the educational process are taken as a basis, can the curriculum be called differentiated. From the first action in determining the creative and intellectual requirements of gifted students of one age or another, we face difficulties in the way of creating a curriculum that develops such students. The individual differences between gifted students are so high that even their age-specific characteristics are far from being left behind. In practice, this is manifested in the fact that until you get acquainted with such a child, we cannot have any ideas about his capabilities and characteristics. As general characteristics of gifted children and their attitude to education, it can be distinguished that they are more interested in far-reaching problems than their peers, focus their gaze not only on the problems of the present, but also on the future, are distinguished by extreme curiosity, developed imagination, creative and logical thinking, advanced knowledge and concepts, independence of discussion and thinking. Looking at this, the special program that we offer represents the initial approaches. The program is a long and continuous (longitudinal) experiment, in which the education of students with a high ability to master directly in the lesson and extracurricular activities is organized, and changes in cognitive processes are observed

This means that in order for us to identify gifted students in the course processes and be able to work with them correctly, it was found in experiments that we need to effectively use various pedagogical-psychological and innovative technologies.

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